

Defining an integrated DMP tool at UWA

An implementation project for the Institutional Underpinnings Program

Project summary report

University of Western Australia

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About the Institutional Underpinnings Program

In partnership with 25 Australian universities, we created a jointly-agreed Research Data Management Framework for Institutions for the management, sharing, retention and disposal of research data. Each partner university conducted projects to validate and test an aspect of the framework in their local contexts. This is a report on one of the projects.

More information

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).

View the [Research Data Management Framework for Institutions](#).

Project Summary

The project sought to define the requirements for a data management planning tool that can assist with the assessment of needs, compliance, provisioning, and ongoing management of research data.

The project was led by the library but involved staff from a variety of areas in the University including University IT, Information Governance, Records and Archives, Office of Research, Human ethics committee and research staff and students.

A core project team worked to produce the following outcomes:

1. A document which defined the purpose and mission of the tool. This includes identifying the problem statement at the University and a description of how the tool will address these issues. The document also features a diagram of the proposed workflow of how the tool might integrate into the various research data management activities associated with the research life cycle. This document drew on the checklist outlined in the [Research Data Management for Institutions Framework](#) Research Data Planning element.
2. A detailed list of functional and metadata field requirements was created. These requirements outlined what they team thought should be included to capture all the essential elements and information for the University and its researchers to be able make informed decisions on how to classify their data, which storage would be appropriate, who could access and work on the data. Also considered was how to push and pull relevant data into and out of the tool for reuse, as well as how to ensure appropriate retention and disposal actions are executed and responsible publishing of data. Input for these requirements were sought from a number of stakeholders via a workshop and some to one to meetings. In addition, several case studies were created based on interviews with the research community at UWA. These drew on the research data planning element, active data management element, retention and disposal element.
3. Six case studies outlining research data management needs from a variety of UWA research groups and disciplines. Potential applications of the new integrated DMP tool were added to these.
4. Two swimlane diagrams were created to visualise how the DMP Management tool interacts in a research project workflow for both Academic staff and HDR students.
5. A list of reporting requirements based on the metadata collected in the new DMP tool.

Resulting Improvements

Benefits of this project include the University having a better understanding of the requirements for our key stakeholders in relation to data planning needs and what they would like from a DMP tool. We have defined and agreed to the requirements for an integrated DMP tool which will provide a more holistic

and coordinated approach to RDM, leverage existing systems and ensure data is appropriately classified, stored and disposed of. We have an agreed roadmap for progressing this work as well as how to support its rollout and use at UWA. And ultimately our research data will be more visible to the University, stored appropriately and have retention and disposal protocols applied as part of the management process.

Next Steps

A business case was presented to the University's Capital Investment Advisory Committee for funding to go forward with procurement and implementation of the integrated DMP tool. This work will be undertaken as a critical research infrastructure project led by Uni IT with support from the University Library and other areas of the University.

Project Outputs

Reusable outputs produced include:

1. Functional and Metadata requirements for an integrated DMP tool.

Access available through our repository:

<https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/datasets/institutional-underpinnings-metadata-and-functional-requirements->

2. Research Data Management Swimlane diagram for Academic Staff.

<https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/datasets/institutional-underpinnings-dmp-workflow-staff>

3. Research Data Management Swimlane diagram for HDR students.

<https://research-repository.uwa.edu.au/en/datasets/institutional-underpinnings-dmp-workflow-hdr-student>

View more outputs of the [Institutional Underpinnings program](#).